

TILSHUNOSLIKNING AMALIY MASALALARI: ZAMONAVIY TILSHUNOSLIKNING DOLZARB MUAMMOLARI, YECHIMLARI, TARAQQIYOTI VA ISTIQBOLLARI

mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman

MATERIALLARI

2025-yil 29-30-sentabr

**O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI OLIY TA’LIM, FAN VA
INNOVATSIYALAR VAZIRLIGI
SIRDARYO VILOYATI HOKIMLIGI
GULISTON DAVLAT UNIVERSITETI,
TURKIYA RESPUBLIKASI BALIKESIR UNIVERSITETI,
TURKIYA RESPUBLIKASI FIRAT UNIVERSITETI,
YANGLING KASB-HUNAR VA TEXNIKA KOLLEJI**

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To‘plamga keltirilgan ma’ruza tezislarning mazmuni, undagi ma’lumotlar va me’yoriy hujjatlar hamda fikr-mulohazalar, takliflarning to‘g‘riligiga mualliflarning o‘zlari mas’uldirlar

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xil: ba'zilar sath hosil qila olsa, ba'zilar yo'q. Ayrimlari yondoshlari bilan birga bitta sathni hosil qiladi.

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POSTSTRUCTURALIST AND COGNITIVE APPROACHES TO THE TRANSFORMATION OF LANGUAGE IDENTITY

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Abstract: This research investigates the development of the concept of language identity from the second half of the 20th century in the context of structuralism and poststructuralism, and its subsequent enrichment through cognitive and psycholinguistic aspects. The approaches of non-linguist thinkers like Z. Freud and J. Lacan, as well as the idea of the “death of the author,” are emphasized as central to the reevaluation of linguistic personality. The influence of the language-thought relationship and the concept of performativity on language identity is analyzed systematically.

Keywords: language identity, structuralism, poststructuralism, cognitive linguistics, psycholinguistics, death of the author

The enrichment of language identity theory through the ideas of non-linguist scholars like Z. Freud and J. Lacan logically directs our research toward evaluating the influence of structuralism and poststructuralism, as well as modernism and postmodernism, on the contemporary concept of linguistic personality. The dominance of the "death of the author" idea in the humanities, as well as the rise of postmodern tolerance and multiculturalism to the level of a global societal format, necessitate tracing the development of the language identity concept within these philosophical currents.

It is now well-known that structuralism's neglect of the worldview, desires, intentions, and interests of the real person behind the text inevitably led L. Weisgerber—the very founder of the language identity idea—away from this theoretical framework toward a different analytical perspective. Following the principle of action and reaction, Weisgerber and his followers, in their search for linguistic personality within texts, often overlooked the structural aspects of language. This shift has resulted in an analytical swing from one pole to another. As L.S. Yermolayeva notes, Weisgerber's elevation of the language-thought connection as a decisive factor significantly reduced the role of other analytical components. This reaction against the structuralist approach gives us a preliminary insight into the role of structuralism and poststructuralism (as a platform of theoretical analysis) in the formation of the language identity concept.

It is appropriate to categorize the research on language identity theory from the second half of the 20th century for systematic evaluation. Although this period significantly contributed to the development of language identity theory, it is characterized by ideological complexity and intense idea generation, making unified analysis difficult. The approach of A.V. Sakharova, who assessed the search for paradigms in language identity studies, is noteworthy. She emphasizes the diversity of theoretical platforms in the field and proposes grouping the research into two directions:

1. Studies targeting transcendental, supra-individual forms of existence, and
2. Analytical concepts based on linguistic performativity and the recognition of human presence in language.

In our view, it is more appropriate to classify research from the second half of the 20th century to the present into two general categories:

1. Research platforms emerging after the crisis of structuralism and their impact on the formation of the language identity idea,
2. The role of cognitive linguistics and psycholinguistics in shaping the modern format of the language identity theory.

As our study focuses on the mechanisms of representing linguistic personality in literary language, it is essential to examine the impact of poststructuralism on the concept of language identity, particularly the role of the “death of the author” concept in identifying linguistic personality.

Conclusion: The study demonstrates that poststructuralism, especially the idea of the “death of the author,” necessitates analyzing language identity not only on a structural level but also on contextual and psychological levels. The notion of the author's disappearance from the text actually opens a path toward a renewed understanding of individual linguistic personality traces within language. Thus, the concept of language identity in the modern era shifts from structural analysis to the multidimensional representation of personality.

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NOMUTANOSIBLIKNING DIAXRON VA SINXRON TAHLILI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada mumtoz adabiyotlarimizda sintagmalarda nomutanosiblikning diaxron va sinxron ko‘rinishlari qiyoslanib tahlil qilingan. Nomutanosiblikning ko‘rinishlari, yuzaga chiqishi tadqiq etilgan. Allomorflarda, kesimlik, egalik, kelishik shakllarida nomutanosiblikning qanday yuzaga chiqishi ilmiy isbotlab berilgan. Maqolaning yozilishida A.Navoiy asarlari tanlab olinib tahlilga tortilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: sinxroniya, diaxroniya, allomorf, kesimlik, egalik, kelishik shakllari, sintagma, nomutanosiblik, fe‘l.

Abstract. This article compares and analyzes the diachronic and synchronous manifestations of asymmetry in syntagmas in our classical literature. The manifestations and manifestations of asymmetry are studied. It is scientifically proven how asymmetry occurs in allomorphs, inflectional, possessive, and conjunctive forms. In writing the article, the works of A. Navoi were selected and analyzed.

Keywords: synchrony, diachrony, allomorph, inflectional, possessive, conjunctive forms, syntagma, asymmetry, verb.

Morfologik sintagmalarda nomutanosiblikning diaxron va sinxron ko‘rinishlarini tadqiq qilish sintagmani semiotikaga, paradigmaga bog‘lab o‘rganishni talab etadi. Har qanday sintagmadagi morfologik shakl(lar) ma‘lum paradigmaga asoslangan bo‘lib, semiotik jihatdan mutanosib yoki nomutanosib bo‘lishi mumkin. Shu sababli paradigmada mavjud bo‘lgan birliklar semiotikaga bog‘liq holda o‘rganiladi. Sintagma ko‘rinishidagi mutanosiblik nutq zanjirida ifoda va mazmun tengma-teng tarzda belgilanishini taqozo etadi, ya‘ni ifodalanuvchi mazmun va shakllar miqdori mos keladi. Bu holat ayni damdagi sinxroniyaning